

Molecular docking, density functional theory, and molecular dynamics study of pipecolisporin derivatives: Unveiling the antimalarial potential of novel cyclic peptides

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Abstract

Malaria remains a persistent global health issue, with escalating resistance to existing antimalarial treatments driving the urgent need for novel therapeutic agents. This study aimed to evaluate the *in silico* antimalarial potential of pipecolisporin analogs by investigating their binding affinity to key *Plasmodium* proteins and assessing their pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles. We employed molecular docking and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to investigate the interactions between pipecolisporin analogs and three key *Plasmodium* proteins: dihydrofolate reductase (2BL9), plasmepsin V (4ZL4), and lactate dehydrogenase (1CET). The pharmacokinetic (ADME) properties and toxicity of the analogs were predicted using cheminformatics tools to assess their potential bioavailability and safety. Among the tested compounds, analog-3 demonstrated the highest binding affinity with 2BL9 (–13.02 kcal/mol) and 4ZL4 (–8.07 kcal/mol). MD simulations confirmed the stability of the analog-3-protein complexes, reinforcing its potential as an effective enzyme inhibitor. ADME predictions showed that all analogs had low gastrointestinal absorption and poor ability to cross the blood-brain barrier. Toxicity assessments indicated the presence of neurotoxic and respiratory risks across all analogs. Despite pharmacokinetic limitations and toxicity concerns, pipecolisporin analogs, particularly analog-3, exhibit strong inhibitory potential against key *Plasmodium* proteins. With further structural optimization to improve bioavailability and reduce toxicity, these compounds hold promise as novel antimalarial agents.

Keywords

Plasmodium protein, pipecolisporin analog, molecular docking study, molecular dynamics simulation, pharmacokinetic properties, antimalarial candidate

Introduction

In 2022, the global malaria burden rose to 249 million cases, up from 244 million in 2021, with 608,000 deaths, predominantly in sub-Saharan Africa. Children under five remain the most vulnerable, accounting for 78% of malaria-related fatalities (Skinner et al. 2024). Despite numerous efforts to control malaria, including widespread distribution of insecticide-treated bed nets and antimalarial drugs, the World Health Organization (WHO) has noted that insufficient progress has been made toward its eradication (Sridharan et al. 2019). Resistance to existing antimalarial treatments, particularly in *Plasmodium falciparum*, has further complicated efforts to eliminate the disease (Antony and Parija 2016). This underscores the urgent need for new therapeutic compounds with enhanced efficacy and reduced resistance potential. Additionally, challenges such as climate change and humanitarian crises have exacerbated malaria transmission in various regions. Nevertheless, positive developments have emerged, including the rollout of new malaria vaccines like RTS,S/AS01 and R21/Matrix-M, as well as the use of dual-active ingredient insecticide-treated nets (Hammershaimb and Berry 2023).

Previous research has shown that traditional medicine, particularly in malaria-endemic regions, has been a source of many antimalarial compounds derived from plants. Flavonoids and other plant-based compounds have demonstrated significant antimalarial activity, forming a foundation for modern drug discovery (Bekono et al. 2020). In various regions around the world, particularly in tropical and subtropical areas where malaria remains endemic, plants have been traditionally used for their medicinal properties. In addition to Mexico and Central America, where plants like *Cecropia obtusifolia*, *Artemisia annua*, and *Cinchona* species have been utilized, many other regions also rely on plant-based remedies (Gachelin et al. 2017; Rivera-Mondragón et al. 2019; Shinyuy et al. 2023). For example, in Asia, *Artemisia annua* (qinghao) has long been used in Chinese traditional medicine and is the source of artemisinin, a critical component of modern malaria treatments (Ding et al. 2020). Similarly, in Africa, plants such as *Azadirachta indica* (neem) and *Cryptolepis sanguinolenta* are known for their antimalarial effects (Osafu et al. 2017; Valery et al. 2023). In India, plants like *Swertia chirata* and *Andrographis paniculata* have been traditionally employed in malaria treatment (Pandey and Pankaj 2007; Salam et al. 2019). Across the globe, research continues to explore the antimalarial potential of local plants, demonstrating that various regions contribute to the discovery and development of new antimalarial drugs.

The development of antimalarial drugs has increasingly relied on advanced computational tools such as computer-aided drug design (CADD) to expedite the drug discovery process. CADD includes various techniques like molecular docking, which allows for the simulation of interactions between drug candidates and target proteins, providing valuable insights into their binding affinity and potential efficacy (Suwendar et al. 2023). Molecular docking is particularly useful for evaluating the inhibitory potential of compounds against key *Plasmodium* proteins

such as dihydrofolate reductase, plasmepsin V, and lactate dehydrogenase (Lobato-Tapia et al. 2023). These proteins play essential roles in the parasite's survival and replication within human hosts, making them prime targets for antimalarial drug development. Dihydrofolate reductase is involved in folate metabolism, which is critical for DNA synthesis in *Plasmodium vivax*, while plasmepsin V is a protease necessary for protein export in *Plasmodium falciparum* (Hodder et al. 2015; Ibraheem et al. 2023). Lactate dehydrogenase, on the other hand, is crucial for energy production in *Plasmodium falciparum*, particularly during the parasite's asexual stages (Lee et al. 2012). By targeting these proteins, new drugs could disrupt the life cycle of the malaria parasite, leading to its eradication from the host.

In recent years, the isolation and synthesis of peptides with antimalarial properties have garnered increasing attention as a viable approach in combating drug-resistant malaria. One promising class of compounds includes various cyclic peptides, known for their ability to inhibit key *Plasmodium* proteins that are essential for the parasite's survival (Sinha et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2023). Pipecolisporin, a cyclic peptide isolated from the endophytic fungus *Nigrospora oryzae*, has been identified for its potential antimalarial activity (Fernández-Pastor et al. 2021). Although there have been no detailed computational studies conducted on pipecolisporin specifically, other antimicrobial peptides, such as newly derived sulfonamide carboxamide alanine-glycine dipeptides (Ugwuja et al. 2019), novel sulfonamide-phenylalanine-glycine dipeptide conjugates (Aronimo et al. 2021), and novel leucine-valine-based dipeptides (Ezugwu et al. 2020), have been successfully modeled through in silico study, synthesized, characterized, and tested for antimalarial activity. The exploration of these antimalarial peptides has opened new research avenues for developing methodologies in the design and development of novel peptides to evaluate their effectiveness as potential antimalarial agents. These efforts aim to improve the yield, efficacy, and bioavailability of such candidate compounds. Most antimicrobial peptides from previous studies have demonstrated the ability to interact with essential proteins in *Plasmodium* species, disrupting their function and inhibiting parasite growth. These studies suggest that cyclic peptides like pipecolisporin are also predicted to become a new frontier in antimalarial drug development.

In this study, we aim to evaluate the biological activity of pipecolisporin analogs through molecular docking and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to assess their interactions with key *Plasmodium* proteins. In addition to computational analyses, we will investigate the pharmacokinetic properties of these analogs, including their absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) profiles. Toxicity predictions will also be conducted to evaluate the safety of these compounds. Given the growing resistance to existing antimalarial treatments, the identification of new compounds with favorable binding properties and minimal toxicity is critical. By targeting essential proteins in the *Plasmodium* life cycle, pipecolisporin analogs could provide a new class of therapeutic agents for malaria treatment. The results of this study will contribute to the ongoing

search for novel antimalarial drugs and provide insights into the potential of pipicolisporin analogs as enzyme inhibitors. Through this research, we hope to identify promising compounds that can be further developed into effective treatments for malaria.

Materials and methods

Computational tools and hardware specifications

The computational analysis in this study was performed using both Windows 10 and Linux Ubuntu 18.10 operating systems. The software utilized includes BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2024 Client 24.1, MGLTools 1.5.7 with AutoDock 4.2.6, PatchDock, PEP-FOLD 3.5, Orca 6.0, Avogadro 1.2.0, Chemcraft, Chimera 1.14, PyMOL 2.5.8, VMD 1.9.2, and GROMACS 2016.3 with the *g_mmpbsa* package for molecular dynamics and binding free energy calculations. Additionally, web-based platforms such as I-TASSER, SwissADME, pKCSM, ProTox-3.0, and Molinspiration were employed for structure prediction, pharmacokinetic analysis, and toxicity assessment. The computational hardware used in this study consisted of a desktop computer with an Intel Core i5-8500 CPU @ 4.30 GHz (6 cores), 16 GB RAM, a 2 TB HDD, a 120 GB SSD, and an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 Ti GPU. These specifications provided sufficient computational power for molecular docking, density functional theory (DFT) calculations, molecular dynamics simulations, and free energy assessments.

Protein preparation

The crystallographic data for essential receptors involved with *Plasmodium vivax* (identifiers 2BL9 (<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/2BL9>) (Kongsaree et al. 2005), 4ZL4 (<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/4ZL4>) (Hodder et al. 2015)), and *Plasmodium falciparum* (identifier 1CET (<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/1CET>) (Read et al. 1999)) were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (accessible at <http://www.rcsb.org/>). These structures were resolved at 1.90 Å, 2.37 Å, and 2.05 Å, respectively. Using the Dock Prep tool within BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2024 Client 24.1, the data underwent several modifications, including the elimination of water molecules, superfluous chains, and bound ligands, in addition to the integration of hydrogen atoms and the assignment of partial charges (BIOVIA 2017). Reconstruction of incomplete protein segments was accomplished using tools provided by I-TASSER (<https://zhanggroup.org/I-TASSER/>) (Zhang 2008).

Preparation and configuration of chemical entities

The pipicolisporin derivatives (analog-1 through analog-6) were sourced in SDF file format from PubChem (available at <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) (Fig. 1). The geometry of these ligands was optimized using Avogadro software version 1.2.0, which also facilitated the conversion of these files to .pdb format (Hanwell et al. 2012). Subsequently, these prepared compounds were employed for docking analysis using the BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2024 Client 24.1 software (BIOVIA 2017).

Figure 1. A two-dimensional diagram of pipicolisporin derivatives for evaluating structure-activity relationships (SAR).

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations

Density Functional Theory (DFT), grounded in quantum mechanics, offers an exceptionally precise representation of electron distribution within molecules, enabling the computation of multiple properties such as molecular energies, geometries, and electronic characteristics. The Orca 6.0 software package was employed to calculate these quantum mechanical properties (Neese 2022). The electronic properties of the molecules were analyzed in their singlet ground state, under neutral conditions, and without solvents, utilizing the B3LYP (Becke, 3-parameter, Lee-Yang-Parr) functional within the DFT framework, combined with a 6-31G basis set. The DFT outcomes were analyzed using the Chemcraft (graphical program for visualization of quantum) (<https://www.chemcraftprog.com/>) (Zhurko and Zhurko 2020) and the Avogadro version 1.2.0 programs (Hanwell et al. 2012). This approach allowed for the assessment of the molecule's reactivity by analyzing key reactivity descriptors, including electron affinity, ionization potential, chemical hardness (η), chemical softness (ζ), electronegativity (χ), electrophilicity (ω), and electronic potential (μ).

Molecular peptide docking analysis

The experimental ligands were accommodated within a uniformly sized grid box measuring $64 \times 60 \times 60$ Å for all structures, ensuring coverage of the entire active site. The coordinates for the grid boxes were set based on the natural ligand's previous positions, providing additional space for ligand flexibility within the docking process: 2BL9 (89.726, 13.626, 34.293), 4ZL4 (-3.040, 99.279, 42.328), and 1CET (36.211, 10.539, 19.830). The Lamarckian genetic algorithm was utilized in conjunction with a rigid receptor framework to identify optimal ligand conformations. Each structure underwent ten separate docking trials using MGLTools 1.5.7 and AutoDockTools (ADT) 4.2.6, from which the most consistent energy and pose across replicates were determined as the definitive outcomes (Forli et al. 2012). Visualization of the docking results was achieved using PyMOL 2.5.8 (Delano 2002) and BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2024 Client 24.1 (BIOVIA 2017), which also facilitated the validation of the docking accuracy by superposing the redocked ligand poses against their co-crystallized forms from the PDB, with RMSD calculations performed in PyMOL 2.5.8 to ensure reliability, aiming for an RMSD under 2 Å (Ariyanto et al. 2023).

Molecular peptide dynamics simulation

Molecular dynamics simulations were performed to evaluate the binding stability, conformational behavior, and interaction modes between the compounds (analog-1 to analog-6) and the receptors (1CET, 2BL9, and 4ZL4). The ligand-receptor complex files were analyzed using GROMACS 2016.3 software for these simulations (Van Der Spoel et al. 2005; Pronk et al. 2013; Abraham et al. 2015). Ligand topologies were generated through the AnteCham-

ber python parser interface (ACYPPE) software (Kagami et al. 2023). For the molecular dynamics (MD) simulation, the complex structures first underwent energy minimization in a vacuum using the steepest descent algorithm for 5000 steps. The solvated complex was then placed in a cubic periodic box with a dimension of 0.5 nm, employing the Simple Point Charge (SPC) water model while maintaining a temperature of 310 K. To further equilibrate the system, Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions were introduced to achieve a salt concentration of 0.15 M. Each complex was subjected to a 50 ns simulation under both NVT and NPT ensembles, ensuring constant particle number, temperature, and pressure. Trajectory analysis, including root mean square deviation (RMSD), root mean square fluctuation (RMSF), radius of gyration (RG), and solvent-accessible surface area (SASA), was conducted using the GROMACS simulation package via the "WebGRO for Macromolecular Simulations" online server (<https://simlab.uams.edu/>) (Paz et al. 2004). Graphs were created using the Xmgrace tool from Microsoft Excel 2013 and Grace Software 5.9 (Turner 2005).

Computational free energy assessment using MM-PBSA

The outcomes of molecular dynamics simulations were employed to determine the binding free energies between the protein-ligand complexes using the MM-PBSA method (Kumari et al. 2014; Wang et al. 2018; Ren et al. 2020). This technique is a reliable and efficient approach for estimating free energy and understanding molecular recognition, particularly in protein-ligand interactions. Ligand binding energies were computed using the `g_mmpbsa` and `MMPBSA.py` script from the GROMACS suite package. The core concept behind this method is to decompose the total free energy of the complex into its various components, including solvation, van der Waals, and electrostatic contributions. The binding free energy is calculated using the equation:

$$\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = \Delta G_{\text{complex}} - [\Delta G_{\text{protein}} + \Delta G_{\text{ligand}}]$$

This equation is further expanded as $\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = \Delta G_{\text{MM}} + \Delta G_{\text{PB}} + \Delta G_{\text{SA}} - T\Delta S$. In this formula, ΔG_{MM} represents the molecular mechanics interactions, which are the sum of electrostatic and van der Waals forces. ΔG_{PB} and ΔG_{SA} denote polar and non-polar solvation energies, respectively, while $T\Delta S$ accounts for the entropic contribution to the binding free energy.

Evaluation of pharmacokinetic and toxicity parameters

The ProTox-3.0 (Prediction of TOXicity of chemicals) (<https://tox.charite.de/prottox3/>) server was employed to forecast the toxicity of the selected compounds, with the input provided in the form of canonical SMILES notation (Banerjee et al. 2018). For calculating the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) properties, the pKCSM (<https://biosig.lab.uq.edu.au/pkcsml/>)

and SwissADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>) platforms, both freely accessible online, were utilized (Daina et al. 2017; Pires et al. 2015). These tools enabled the prediction of various pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic attributes of the compounds. The biological activity of three compounds was assessed using the Molinspiration (<https://www.molinspiration.com/>) server, where a bioactivity score of > 0 indicated biologically active compounds, a range of -5.0 to < 0 signified moderate activity, and a score of < -5.0 indicated biologically inactive compounds.

Results

Quantum mechanical insights from frontier orbitals

Frontier molecular orbital (FMO) analysis is a quantum chemistry computational method used to examine the energy levels, configuration, and electron distribution of a molecule's highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). HOMO-LUMO analysis is performed to determine the reactivity of molecular orbitals in organic compounds (Tanaka and Chujo 2021). Molecules with minimal or non-existent HOMO-LUMO gaps are typically more reactive. This area of chemistry is explored for potential inhibitors. FMO calculations assess pipecolisporin derivatives regarding their ionization potential and electron affinity. The electronic descriptors examined include parameters like EHOMO, ELUMO, ΔE_{gap} , ionization potential, electron affinity, electronegativity, chemical potential, hardness, softness, electronic potential, and electrophilicity, with the results presented in Fig. 2, Table 1. In quantum chemistry, electronic energy (Eh) plays a critical role in computational techniques for analyzing molecular behavior. Differences in Eh reveal variations in the stability and bonding interactions of these compounds. Higher energy values indicate more reactive molecules. Analog-3 registered the lowest energy at -2431.659809 Eh, while analog-1 showed the highest energy at -2264.156 Eh. Additionally, analog-3 exhibited the highest dipole moment at 9.9702 D, while analog-1 recorded the lowest at 4.2718 D. Meanwhile, the

other pipecolisporin analogs displayed intermediate dipole moments: 9.7271 D (analog-2), 7.6997 D (analog-4), 5.0153 D (analog-5), and 6.4377 D (analog-6). These dipole moment differences indicate variations in charge distribution and polarity, with analog-3 being highly polar and analog-1 relatively less polar.

The EHOMO values spanned from -0.18243 to -0.20167 eV, with analog-3 showing the lowest and analog-5 reaching the highest. ELUMO values ranged between -0.00058 and -0.01193 eV, where analog-6 exhibited the lowest and analog-5 the highest readings. The energy gap (ΔE_{gap}) extended from -0.18185 to -0.19202 eV, with analog-1 demonstrating the broadest gap. Ionization potential fluctuated from 0.18243 eV to 0.20167 eV. Electronegativity varied from 0.896109 to 0.924093 , with analog-4 registering the highest. Chemical potential values were found between 0.091505 and 0.10619 eV. Hardness ranged from 0.090925 to 0.09601 eV, with analog-1 having the greatest hardness. Softness spanned from 5.207790855 to 5.499037668 eV $^{-1}$. Electronic potential oscillated between -0.091505 and -0.10557 eV. Electrophilicity ranged from 0.04604435 to 0.059509958 eV.

The key compounds display distinct electronic characteristics when compared with each other. Notably, analog-3 features a significantly lower EHOMO and a notably tighter energy gap, suggesting it behaves differently in terms of electronic structure relative to the others. Analog-6, with the lowest ELUMO, also demonstrates higher values for electronegativity and softness, highlighting unique patterns in electron arrangement and reactivity. Analog-5, on the other hand, has the most elevated EHOMO and ELUMO values, alongside a higher ionization potential, pointing to a unique ionization profile among the group. Furthermore, their variances in electronegativity and electrophilicity signal distinct chemical reactivity and interaction potentials, particularly in contrast with the reference molecule, analog-1.

Molecular peptide docking analysis

Molecular docking analysis was conducted to evaluate the interaction potential between pipecolisporin derivative compounds and specific target proteins.

Table 1. The global reactivity descriptors (in eV) for four selected compounds were calculated using the DFT B3LYP/6-31G method, based on the energy levels of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals.

Properties	Analog-1	Analog-2	Analog-3	Analog-4	Analog-5	Analog-6
Electronic energy (Eh)	-2264.156	-2319.183464	-2431.659809	-2428.09052	-2319.194922	-2319.173796
Dipole moment (D)	4.2718	9.7271	9.9702	7.6997	5.0153	6.4377
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-0.19810	-0.19965	-0.20167	-0.19296	-0.18243	-0.19921
E_{LUMO} (eV)	-0.00608	-0.01142	-0.01071	-0.00731	-0.00058	-0.01193
ΔE_{gap} (eV)	-0.19202	-0.18823	-0.19096	-0.18565	-0.18185	-0.18728
Ionization potential (eV)	0.1981	0.19965	0.20167	0.19296	0.18243	0.19921
Electron affinity (eV)	0.00608	0.01142	0.01071	0.00731	0.00058	0.01193
Electronegativity (eV)	0.896109	0.913784	0.909338	0.924093	0.914044	0.910748
Chemical potential (eV)	0.10209	0.105535	0.10619	0.100135	0.091505	0.10557
Hardness (eV)	0.09601	0.094115	0.09548	0.092825	0.090925	0.09364
Softness (eV $^{-1}$)	5.207790855	5.312649418	5.236698785	5.386479935	5.499037668	5.339598462
Electronic potential (eV)	-0.10209	-0.105535	-0.10619	-0.100135	-0.091505	-0.10557
Electrophilicity (eV)	0.054277513	0.059170357	0.059050671	0.054010332	0.04604435	0.059509958

Figure 2. The diagram illustrates the arrangement of molecular orbitals in their lowest energy configuration.

The docking process was carried out using MGLTools 1.5.7 and AutoDockTools (ADT) 4.2.6 to determine the binding energy values, which serve as indicators of molecular affinity. The selected target proteins, 2BL9, 4ZL4, and 1CET, are crucial in malaria treatment and possess well-defined binding sites within their crystalline structures, as documented in the .pdb file. The docking simulation was performed using a grid dimension of $64 \times 60 \times 60$ Å. The results demonstrated that all compounds exhibited binding energies below

-6.06 kcal/mol (Table 2), with the most stable complexes being Analog-3-2BL9 (-13.02 kcal/mol), Analog-3-4ZL4 (-8.07 kcal/mol), and Analog-3-1CET (-13.02 kcal/mol). Notably, the majority of ligands analyzed displayed stronger binding affinities compared to the threshold value. This suggests that pipicolisporin derivatives possess significant inhibitory potential against the selected target proteins, making them promising candidates for further investigation in the development of antimalarial agents.

Table 2. Ligand-binding strengths and interactions with amino acid residues.

Receptor Target	Pipicolisporin Compound	Molecular Affinity	Inhibitory Value	Residue Interaction	Classification	Type of Interaction			
2BL9	Analog-1	−10.67 kcal/mol	15.03 nM (nanomolar)	A:LEU45	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
				A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
				A:ASP53	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion			
				A:LYS48	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
				A:CYS49	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
				A:MET54	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
				A:PRO122	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
				A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
				A:ILE121	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
				A:ALA15	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			
				A:ALA15	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			
				A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			
				Analog-2	−11.05 kcal/mol	7.95 nM (nanomolar)	A:TRP47	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
							A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond							
A:THR44	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond							
A:LEU45 A:TYR125	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond							
A:ALA15	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma							
A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Alkyl							
A:MET54	Hydrophobic	Alkyl							
A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Alkyl							
A:LEU128	Hydrophobic	Alkyl							
A:PRO129	Hydrophobic	Alkyl							
A:TRP47	Hydrophobic	Alkyl							
A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl							
A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl							
Analog-3	−13.02 kcal/mol	284.71 pM (picomolar)	A:SER120	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:MET54	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond				
			A:ARG131	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Cation				
			A:ARG131	Electrostatic	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond				
			A:LEU45	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond				
			A:THR44	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma				
			A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
			A:MET54 A:ILE13	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
			A:TRP47	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
			A:PHE57 A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl				
			A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl				
			A:LEU128	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl				
				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl				
Analog-4	−10.36 kcal/mol	25.40 nM (nanomolar)	A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Salt Bridge				
			A:ASP53	Electrostatic	Attractive Charge				
			A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:CYS49	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:TYR125	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond				
			A:LEU128	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
			A:ILE121	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
			A:CYS49	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl				
			A:MET54	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl				
Analog-5	−10.78 kcal/mol	12.57 nM (nanomolar)	A:CYS49 A:TYR125	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:ASP53 A:ASP53						
			A:ARG131	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:TYR125	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:MET54	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
			A:LEU45	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation				
			A:MET54	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma				
			A:TRP47 A:TYR125	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
			A:LEU128						
			A:PRO129	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
				Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl				
	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl							
	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl							
	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl							
	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl							

Receptor Target	Pipicolisporin Compound	Molecular Affinity	Inhibitory Value	Residue Interaction	Classification	Type of Interaction		
2BL9	Analog-6	-10.01 kcal/mol	46.27 nM (nanomolar)	A:SER117	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:SER117	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:SER117	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:ALA15 A:ILE121	Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
				A:LEU128	Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
				A:LEU45	Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
				A:PHE57 A:MET54	Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
				A:CYS49	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				A:MET54	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
4ZL4	Analog-1	-6.49 kcal/mol	17.39 uM (micromolar)	A:GLU141	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:ASN435	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:VAL434	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond		
				A:VAL434	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma		
				A:HIS320	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped		
				A:VAL434	Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
				A:CYS140	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				A:CYS140	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				A:VAL434	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				A:LYS437	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				A:ILE439	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				Analog-2	-7.22 kcal/mol	5.13 uM (micromolar)	A:GLU431	Hydrogen Bond
	A:TYR59 A:ASP387	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond					
	A:PHE318	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond					
	A:LEU179	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped					
	Analog-3	-8.07 kcal/mol	1.21 uM (micromolar)	A:THR317	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:ASP57 A:GLU431	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:GLU431	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:TYR59	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
				A:ALA60	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond		
				A:LEU179	Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
A:PHE318				Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
A:HIS320 A:ALA60				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			
A:LEU179				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			
Analog-4	-6.91 kcal/mol	8.54 uM (micromolar)	A:GLU141	Hydrogen Bond	Salt Bridge			
			A:GLU141	Electrostatic	Attractive Charge			
			A:GLY315	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:GLU141	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:GLY315	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:GLU431	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:VAL434	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma			
			A:LEU179	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			
			A:VAL434	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			
			Analog-5	-6.89 kcal/mol	8.90 uM (micromolar)	A:CYS140	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl
						A:LEU179	Hydrophobic	Alkyl
						A:VAL434	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl
						A:GLU141	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
						A:GLU431	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
						A:ALA60	Hydrophobic	Alkyl
A:HIS320	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked						
A:HIS320	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked						
A:VAL434	Hydrophobic	Alkyl						
Analog-6	-6.99 kcal/mol	7.54 uM (micromolar)	A:THR317	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:ILE56	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:ASP57	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:GLU43	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			
			A:GLU58	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			

Receptor Target	Pipicolisporin Compound	Molecular Affinity	Inhibitory Value	Residue Interaction	Classification	Type of Interaction	
4ZL4	Analog-6	−6.99 kcal/mol	7.54 uM (micromolar)	A:ALA60	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	
				A:ALA60	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
				A:LEU179	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
				A:PHE318	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
				A:ALA60	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
1CET	Analog-1	−6.84 kcal/mol	9.64 uM (micromolar)	A:GLU122 A:GLU122	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
				A:ILE119	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
				A:TYR85	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	
				A:TYR85	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	
				A:ILE54	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	
				A:ALA98	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
				A:LYS118	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
				A:ILE119	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
				A:ILE54	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
				A:ILE119	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
	A:ILE119	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
	A:PHE100	Hydrophobic	Alkyl				
					Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
		Analog-2	−6.91 kcal/mol	8.66 uM (micromolar)	A:TYR85	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
	A:GLU122				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
	A:GLU122				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
	A:GLU122				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
	A:ILE54				Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	
	A:ILE54				Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	
	A:ILE54 A:ILE54				Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
	A:ILE119				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
	A:ALA98				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
	A:ILE119				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
					Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
		Analog-3	−7.28 kcal/mol	4.60 uM (micromolar)	A:GLU122	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
	A:GLU122 A:GLU122				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
	A:ILE119 A:ILE54				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
	A:LYS118				Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
	A:LYS118				Hydrophobic	Alkyl	
					Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
					Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	
		Analog-4	−6.06 kcal/mol	36.01 uM (micromolar)	A:ASP53	Electrostatic	Attractive Charge
	A:ASP53				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond				Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
A:ILE54	Hydrophobic				Pi-Sigma		
A:ILE54	Hydrophobic				Alkyl		
A:PHE100	Hydrophobic				Pi-Alkyl		
A:ILE54	Hydrophobic				Pi-Alkyl		
A:VAL55	Hydrophobic				Pi-Alkyl		
	Analog-5	−6.64 kcal/mol	13.63 uM (micromolar)	A:GLU122 A:GLU122	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
A:TYR85				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
A:GLU122				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
A:PHE100 A:LEU115				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
A:ILE119				Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped		
A:ILE54				Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
A:PHE100				Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
							Hydrophobic
	Analog-6	−6.65 kcal/mol	13.31 uM (micromolar)	A:LYS118 A:ASP53	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	
A:LYS118				Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond		
A:LYS118				Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Cation		
A:ILE54				Electrostatic	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond		
A:ILE119				Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
A:PHE100				Hydrophobic	Alkyl		
A:PHE100				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
A:LYS118				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
A:ILE121				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
A:LYS118				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		
				Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl		

Based on previous studies conducted on the original, unmodified pipicolisporin, this compound exhibited its highest binding affinity towards the 2BL9 target, with a value of -10.26 kcal/mol and an inhibition constant of 29.90 nM, indicating strong inhibitory potential. However, for the 1CET and 4ZL4 targets, pipicolisporin showed lower binding affinities of -6.59 kcal/mol and -5.38 kcal/mol, respectively (Kurniaty et al. 2025). These results suggest that pipicolisporin's interaction with 1CET and 4ZL4 is relatively weaker compared to its modified analogs. Analog-3, a structurally modified derivative of pipicolisporin, demonstrated a significant improvement in binding affinity across all targets. Specifically, for 2BL9 and 1CET, analog-3 formed more stable complexes, with binding affinities exceeding -13.02 kcal/mol. The more negative binding affinity values indicate a stronger and more stable ligand-target interaction, which likely contributes to better inhibitory effects. This striking difference highlights analog-3 as a more potent candidate compared to the original pipicolisporin and suggests its potential as a lead compound for further drug development.

When compared with previously studied small molecules, analog-3 demonstrated superior binding affinity, particularly against 2BL9. Studies have shown that some small molecules exhibited binding affinities of -8.70 kcal/mol to -8.50 kcal/mol for 2BL9, which are significantly weaker than Analog-3's binding affinity of -13.02 kcal/mol. This reinforces analog-3 as a highly potent dihydrofolate reductase inhibitor. However, against 4ZL4, certain small molecules outperformed analog-3, with reported binding affinities ranging from -9.60 kcal/mol to -8.30 kcal/mol, compared to analog-3's -8.07 kcal/mol. Similarly, for 1CET, analog-3 (-13.02 kcal/mol) exhibited a stronger binding affinity than chloroquine (-6.30 kcal/mol) but was weaker than some other reported small molecules, which had affinities of -9.10 kcal/mol and -7.90 kcal/mol (Lobato-Tapia et al. 2023; Moreno-Hernández et al. 2023). These findings suggest that while analog-3 is a strong inhibitor of 2BL9, its interaction with 4ZL4 and 1CET may require structural modifications to improve its efficacy. Enhancing its molecular interactions through targeted modifications could increase its potential as a multi-target antimalarial agent. Further studies should explore how structural refinements could optimize analog-3 for broader therapeutic applications.

Fig. 3 displays the binding sites and orientation poses of the three complexes. The interactions between these compounds and the target proteins were mapped and visualized using PyMOL 2.5.8 and BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2024 Client 24.1. The binding affinity values indicate the strength of the interaction between the ligand and the target protein, with more negative values reflecting stronger interactions. Among all the analogs, analog-3 exhibited the highest binding affinity towards the 2BL9 target with a value of -13.02 kcal/mol, as well as a very low inhibition constant of 284.71 pM, indicating a high potential for inhibition. By comparison, analog-1 and analog-2 showed lower binding affinity values, ranging from -10.67 to -11.05 kcal/mol, but still demonstrated fairly

strong interactions with the target proteins. For the 1CET and 4ZL4 targets, Analog-3 also had better binding affinity values compared to the other analogs, with values of -7.28 kcal/mol and -8.07 kcal/mol, respectively. The low inhibition constants for analog-3 suggest that this compound has potential as an effective inhibitor in protein-ligand binding processes. In contrast, the higher inhibition constants in the other analogs indicate that they may be less effective as inhibitors compared to analog-3.

In each visualization, the position of the ligand within the receptor's binding pocket is clearly depicted, highlighting how analog-3 interacts with the surrounding amino acids. The visible hydrogen bonds help stabilize the ligand-receptor interaction, while hydrophobic interactions support the ligand's affinity for the protein. In the complex with 2BL9, analog-3 exhibits several strong hydrophobic interactions, particularly with residues LEU45 and MET54. In the interaction with 4ZL4, hydrogen bonding is more dominant, providing a balance between stability and flexibility of the complex. The visualization for 1CET shows a combination of hydrogen and hydrophobic bonds, offering a comprehensive view of how analog-3 modulates binding in various protein environments. This visualization is crucial for understanding molecular binding mechanisms and guiding further drug development.

Molecular peptide dynamics simulation

Following the assessment of protein-ligand interactions and the achievement of favorable results, molecular dynamics (MD) analysis was performed on the ligands exhibiting the highest binding affinities to evaluate the stability of the protein-ligand complexes (Rizkita et al. 2024). MD simulations were carried out for a duration of 500 ns on the complexes with the lowest binding affinity, specifically analog-2-2BL9, analog-3-2BL9, analog-2-4ZL4, analog-3-4ZL4, analog-2-1CET, and analog-3-1CET. To evaluate the structural stability and fluctuations of these complexes, trajectory analyses were conducted using root mean square deviation (RMSD), root mean square fluctuation (RMSF), radius of gyration (RG), and solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) metrics. These analyses provide insights into the dynamic behavior of the complexes over time, revealing any significant conformational changes. Understanding these fluctuations is essential for predicting the binding stability and potential efficacy of the ligands in practical applications.

The RMSD of the protein backbone was tracked throughout the 500 ns simulation to assess the structural stability and fluctuations (Fig. 4). In the case of the Analog-2-2BL9 complex, notable deviations were observed, with RMSD peaking at around 0.3 nm during the initial 100 ns, after which the system gradually stabilized and maintained steady values for the remainder of the simulation. Conversely, the analog-3-2BL9 complex reached equilibrium earlier with fewer fluctuations, indicating a higher degree of structural stability. For the analog-2-4ZL4 complex, RMSD fluctuated between 0.2 and 0.4 nm for the first 200 ns before settling into a stable conformation.

Figure 3. The two-dimensional and three-dimensional depictions illustrate the hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions between the ligands and the binding cavities of the receptors.

Meanwhile, the analog-3–4ZL4 complex showed consistent stability from the start of the simulation. The analog-2–1CET complex exhibited variations up to 0.25 nm

before stabilizing around the 100 ns mark, whereas the Analog-3–1CET complex displayed smoother transitions and remained more stable throughout the entire period.

Figure 4. The RMSD and RMSF graphs for the 500 ns molecular dynamics simulation of Analog-2-2BL9, Analog-3-2BL9, Analog-2-4ZL4, Analog-3-4ZL4, Analog-2-1CET, and Analog-3-1CET.

Overall, analog-3 complexes consistently demonstrated superior stability compared to analog-2, implying stronger binding interactions and better affinity for the target proteins.

The RMSF analysis provides insights into residue flexibility across the 500 ns simulation, highlighting key differences between analog-2 and analog-3 complexes. In the analog-2-2BL9 complex, fluctuations peaked around residue 150 at 0.5 nm, whereas analog-3-2BL9 exhibited lower fluctuations, suggesting better stability. Similarly, analog-2-4ZL4 showed high RMSF values near residues 50, 200, and 400, while analog-3-4ZL4 had a smoother fluctuation pattern. For analog-2-1CET, a notable peak around residue 250 reached nearly 0.45 nm, whereas analog-3-1CET displayed more uniform fluctuations. In all cases, analog-3 derivatives exhibited reduced fluctuations, indicating stronger binding stability. The consistently low-

er RMSF values in analog-3 complexes support the RMSD findings, reinforcing their structural rigidity. High RMSF peaks in analog-2 suggest flexible regions or surface-exposed loops that may impact binding efficiency. These variations in residue flexibility further emphasize differences in the dynamic behavior of the two analog series.

The radius of gyration (Rg) values were analyzed to assess the compactness and structural flexibility of the protein-ligand complexes over the simulation time (Fig. 5). For the analog-2-2BL9 complex, the Rg values initially decreased during the first 10 ns before stabilizing for the remainder of the 500 ns simulation. A similar trend was observed for the analog-3-2BL9 complex, but with less fluctuation, indicating improved structural stability. In the case of analog-2-4ZL4, the Rg values also dropped after 10 ns, followed by minor fluctuations, while analog-3-4ZL4 maintained steady Rg values

Figure 5. The radius of gyration (Rg) and solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) graphs for the 500 ns molecular dynamics simulations of Analog-2-2BL9, Analog-3-2BL9, Analog-2-4ZL4, Analog-3-4ZL4, Analog-2-1CET, and Analog-3-1CET.

throughout the simulation, indicating more consistent structural integrity. The analog-2-1CET complex showed an increase in Rg after 15 ns, which then remained stable, whereas the analog-3-1CET complex maintained lower and more stable Rg values over the entire simulation.

Solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) values were also plotted over time to evaluate the exposure of the complex to the solvent (Fig. 5). In all complexes, SASA values decreased during the initial 20 ns of the simulation. The analog-3-1CET and analog-3-4ZL4 complexes exhibited a greater reduction in SASA compared to their analog-2 counterparts, indicating that the analog-3 complexes were more compact and less exposed to the solvent. Conversely, the analog-2-2BL9 complex retained higher SASA values than the analog-3-2BL9 complex, suggesting a looser structure. These results, based on both Rg and SASA data, suggest that the analog-3 complexes, especially with 4ZL4

and 1CET, displayed superior structural stability and compactness compared to their analog-2 counterparts.

Pipecolisporin molecular profiles

The MM-PBSA approach was utilized to evaluate the interactions and binding energies between pipecolisporin compounds and their receptor targets. These simulations provided an estimation of how analog-2 and analog-3 bind with three receptors: 2BL9, 4ZL4, and 1CET (Table 3). In this analysis, the binding energies serve as an indicator of the strength of the compound-receptor interactions. Stronger negative values generally reflect more stable and favorable interactions, though they do not directly indicate binding presence or absence. It is important to recognize that these energy values are qualitative, as factors like entropy are not fully accounted for (Mishra et al. 2022).

Table 3. Interaction energies and binding energies with various receptor targets.

Receptor Target	Pipecolisporin Compound	van der Waal Energy	Electrostatic Energy	Polar Solvation Energy	SASA Energy	Binding Energy
2BL9	Analog-2	-239.972 +/- 26.886 kJ/mol	-35.206 +/- 17.243 kJ/mol	167.286 +/- 28.002 kJ/mol	-27.279 +/- 2.247 kJ/mol	-135.171 +/- 16.456 kJ/mol
	Analog-3	-245.322 +/- 19.641 kJ/mol	-62.626 +/- 12.899 kJ/mol	204.279 +/- 30.805 kJ/mol	-26.384 +/- 1.460 kJ/mol	-130.053 +/- 16.713 kJ/mol
4ZL4	Analog-2	-166.391 +/- 19.719 kJ/mol	-20.319 +/- 22.485 kJ/mol	128.862 +/- 29.736 kJ/mol	-19.418 +/- 2.123 kJ/mol	-77.266 +/- 20.757 kJ/mol
	Analog-3	-117.754 +/- 28.406 kJ/mol	-31.247 +/- 30.912 kJ/mol	87.962 +/- 31.182 kJ/mol	-13.145 +/- 3.343 kJ/mol	-74.184 +/- 28.429 kJ/mol
1CET	Analog-2	-138.726 +/- 32.181 kJ/mol	-33.369 +/- 19.713 kJ/mol	100.347 +/- 42.146 kJ/mol	-16.704 +/- 3.280 kJ/mol	-88.453 +/- 30.267 kJ/mol
	Analog-3	-105.654 +/- 31.441 kJ/mol	-26.064 +/- 22.681 kJ/mol	85.468 +/- 42.486 kJ/mol	-13.39 +/- 3.880 kJ/mol	-59.645 +/- 36.700 kJ/mol

Table 4. Analyzed physicochemical and pharmacological characteristics.

Parameters	Analog-1	Analog-2	Analog-3	Analog-4	Analog-5	Analog-6
Physicochemical parameters						
Formula	C37H53N7O6	C37H54N8O6	C40H52N8O6	C37H54N10O6	C37H54N8O6	C37H54N8O6
Molecular weight	691.86 g/mol	706.87 g/mol	740.89 g/mol	734.89 g/mol	706.87 g/mol	706.87 g/mol
Number heavy atoms	50	51	54	53	51	51
Number aromatic heavy atoms	9	9	15	9	9	9
Fraction Csp3	0.62	0.62	0.50	0.59	0.62	0.62
Number rotatable bonds	6	8	8	9	8	8
Number H-bond acceptors	6	7	7	7	7	7
Num. H-bond donors	5	6	6	8	6	6
Molar Refractivity	213.21	215.91	225.98	222.31	215.91	215.91
TPSA	172.81 Å ²	198.83 Å ²	198.83 Å ²	234.71 Å ²	198.83 Å ²	198.83 Å ²
Pharmacological parameters						
Lipinski	No; 2 violations: MW>500, NorO>10	No; 3 violations: MW>500, NorO>10, NHorOH>5	No; 3 violations: MW>500, NorO>10, NHorOH>5	No; 3 violations: MW>500, NorO>10, NHorOH>5	No; 3 violations: MW>500, NorO>10, NHorOH>5	No; 3 violations: MW>500, NorO>10, NHorOH>5
Ghose	No; 3 violations: MW>480, MR>130, #atoms>70	No; 4 violations: WLOGP<-0.4, MR>130, #atoms>70	No; 4 violations: MW>480, WLOGP<-0.4, MR>130, #atoms>70			
Veber	No; 1 violation: TPSA>140	No; 1 violation: TPSA>140	No; 1 violation: TPSA>140	No; 1 violation: TPSA>140	No; 1 violation: TPSA>140	No; 1 violation: TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	No; 2 violations: MW>600, TPSA>150	No; 3 violations: MW>600, TPSA>150, H-don>5	No; 3 violations: MW>600, TPSA>150, H-don>5	No; 3 violations: MW>600, TPSA>150, H-don>5	No; 3 violations: MW>600, TPSA>150, H-don>5	No; 3 violations: MW>600, TPSA>150, H-don>5
Bioavailability Score	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
PAINS	0 alert	0 alert	0 alert	0 alert	0 alert	0 alert
Brenk	0 alert	0 alert	0 alert	2 alerts: imine_1, imine_2	0 alert	0 alert
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, XLOGP3>3.5	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	6.55	6.62	6.56	6.82	6.52	6.55

The binding energies for analog-2 and analog-3 varied across receptor targets. For instance, analog-2 showed a binding energy of -135.171 kJ/mol with 2BL9, suggesting a robust interaction, while analog-3 displayed a slightly higher binding energy of -130.053 kJ/mol. This trend is observed in other receptor targets, where analog-3 consistently exhibits higher binding energies than analog-2, yet both show strong interactions.

Additional energy factors, such as van der Waals, electrostatic, polar solvation, and SASA energy, highlight the different interaction mechanisms. For example, the electrostatic interaction for analog-3 with 2BL9, at -62.626 kJ/mol, is notably stronger than that of analog-2 at -35.206 kJ/mol. The MM-PBSA analysis adds depth to molecular docking by offering a clearer and more precise calculation of binding energies, incorporating solvation effects and flexibility of the compounds. The binding energy calculations show

that both analog-2 and analog-3 form highly stable complexes with the receptors, positioning them as promising leads for further drug development, especially considering their strong interactions across different receptor targets.

In terms of pharmacological properties, all the analogs violate Lipinski's rule of five, with common violations related to high molecular weight (MW>500) and an excessive number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors (Table 4). For example, analog-2 and analog-3 have 6 and 7 hydrogen bond acceptors, respectively, exceeding the typical threshold in Lipinski's rule. This indicates that while these analogs may have strong biological interaction potential, their oral bioavailability could be problematic. Additionally, the high topological polar surface area (TPSA) across all analogs (e.g., 234.71 Å² for analog-4) further complicates their absorption through cell membranes, posing a barrier to efficient drug delivery.

Despite these challenges in drug-likeness properties, it is important to note that none of the analogs trigger any pan assay interference compounds (PAINS) alerts, meaning they are unlikely to produce false positives in biological assays. Therefore, while there are concerns related to pharmacokinetics and bioavailability, pipicolisporin analogs remain promising candidates for further research, with necessary modifications and optimizations to improve their pharmacological profiles and bioavailability.

The toxicity profiles of the pipicolisporin analogs (analog-1 through analog-6) reveal significant insights regarding their safety and potential pharmacological effects (Fig. 6). Each analog is associated with a predicted LD_{50} value, indicating the amount required to cause lethality in 50% of a test population. For instance, analog-1 and analog-6 have a predicted LD_{50} of 1200 mg/kg and fall under toxicity class 4, suggesting moderate toxicity. In contrast, analog-2, analog-3,

Figure 6. Predicted toxicity profiles and ADME characteristics.

and analog-5 are classified as toxicity class 3 with a lower predicted LD₅₀ of 300 mg/kg, indicating a higher risk of toxicity. Analog-4 also exhibits a predicted LD₅₀ of 1250 mg/kg and belongs to toxicity class 4, further emphasizing the variability in toxicity across the analogs. In addition to LD₅₀ values, the average similarity across all analogs is around 64–65%, with a consistent prediction accuracy of approximately 68.07%. This similarity index is crucial as it highlights how closely related these analogs are to known compounds with established toxicological profiles. The predictions suggest that while some analogs may present lower toxicity risks, others warrant careful evaluation due to their higher toxicity classifications. Overall, these findings provide essential guidance for further studies on the safety and efficacy of these compounds in drug development.

From the pharmacokinetic and toxicity evaluation, all analogs showed low gastrointestinal absorption, an inability to cross the blood-brain barrier, and functioned as P-gp substrates, which could affect bioavailability. Although they are not hepatotoxic or cardiotoxic, all analogs have neurotoxic potential and toxicity effects on the respiratory and immune systems. Their biological activity against targets such as GPCRs, ion channel modulators, and kinases showed low potential, although some analogs exhibited slight activity as protease inhibitors. This aligns

with predictions made using Molinspiration's Bioavailability Suite, which utilizes chemical descriptors and machine learning/QSAR models to predict bioactivity scores. Based on the data in Table 5, all analogs demonstrated low bioactivity as GPCR ligands, ion channel modulators, and kinase inhibitors, with values indicating weak or insignificant activity. However, they did exhibit slight activity as protease inhibitors, which could be explored further for potential therapeutic applications. Despite these low activity scores, the analogs show some promise, particularly as enzyme inhibitors. However, their overall therapeutic potential remains limited without further structural optimization. These findings suggest that while immediate applications are limited, modifications could enhance their viability in specific therapeutic areas.

The chart in Fig. 7 shows a breakdown of the biological activity of six different analogs, focusing on Family A G protein-coupled receptors (GPCR), protease, and other entities. All analogs exhibit significant activity toward GPCRs, with analog-6 showing the highest at 93.3% and analog-1 the lowest at 66.7%. This suggests that GPCRs are the primary target for these analogs, which could influence cell signaling pathways. Protease activity is present in all analogs, but in smaller proportions, ranging from 13.3% in analog-1 to 6.7% in analog-6. Protease inhibition can be important for therapeutic interventions,

Table 5. Evaluation of pharmacokinetics, toxicity, and biological activity.

Parameters	Analog-1	Analog-2	Analog-3	Analog-4	Analog-5	Analog-6
ADME						
GI absorption	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
BBB permeant	No	No	No	No	No	No
P-gp substrate	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Log Kp (skin permeation)	-7.82 cm/s	-9.37 cm/s	-9.39 cm/s	-9.96 cm/s	-9.37 cm/s	-9.01 cm/s
Consensus Log Po/w	1.97	0.81	1.08	0.44	1.05	1.04
Log S (ESOL)	-6.26	-4.93	-5.38	-4.66	-4.93	-5.24
Toxicity						
Hepatotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Neurotoxicity	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active
Nephrotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Respiratory toxicity	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active
Cardiotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Carcinogenicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Immunotoxicity	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active
Mutagenicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Cytotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
BBB-barrier	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Ecotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Clinical toxicity	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active
Nutritional toxicity	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Active	Active
Bioactivity						
GPCR ligand	-0.24	-0.32	-0.76	-0.55	-0.29	-0.30
Ion channel modulator	-1.30	-1.46	-2.04	-1.81	-1.41	-1.39
Kinase inhibitor	-0.99	-1.10	-1.62	-1.51	-1.07	-1.05
Nuclear receptor ligand	-1.28	-1.49	-1.97	-2.00	-1.37	-1.35
Protease inhibitor	0.23	0.16	-0.27	0.04	0.16	0.16
Enzyme inhibitor	-0.76	-0.85	-1.38	-1.17	-0.86	-0.87

Figure 7. Comparison of biological activity profiles of six analogs targeting GPCRs, proteases, and other entities.

particularly in diseases where protease activity is detrimental. Some analogs, specifically Analog-1 through Analog-4, display activity toward an entity labeled “Eraser,” potentially linked to gene regulation or epigenetic mechanisms. This activity varies, indicating a secondary but relevant biological role for these analogs. Interestingly, only analog-4 exhibits activity toward an unclassified protein, suggesting unique characteristics that warrant further exploration. Overall, while GPCR activity dominates, variations in protease and “Eraser” activity may provide additional therapeutic opportunities. Each analog shows distinct activity profiles that could be leveraged for specific medical applications depending on the targets involved.

Discussion

Pipicolisporin analogs were evaluated for their therapeutic potential, particularly in terms of binding affinity, stability, pharmacokinetics, and toxicity. Like the ongoing global efforts to combat malaria, where new compounds are continuously sought to inhibit *Plasmodium* spp., these analogs offer promise as potential therapeutic agents for diseases where enzyme inhibition is critical (Fernández-Pastor et al. 2021). The molecular docking results revealed that analog-3 exhibited the highest binding affinity, especially toward 2BL9 and 4ZL4, indicating its potential as a strong inhibitor.

Compared to the original pipecolisporin, analog-3 demonstrated improved binding energy, suggesting that modifications in its structure led to stronger ligand-protein interactions. The docking studies also showed that analog-2 had moderate binding affinity, but it was consistently lower than analog-3, indicating weaker interactions. The binding site interactions of analog-3 included a combination of hydrogen bonds, electrostatic forces, and hydrophobic interactions, which contributed to its higher stability. These docking results provided an initial indication of analog-3's potential as a lead compound for further studies. However, molecular docking alone is insufficient to confirm the stability and dynamic behavior of these interactions (Forli et al. 2016). Therefore, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed to evaluate the stability of analog-3 and analog-2 complexes over time.

Molecular dynamics simulations further confirmed that analog-3 formed highly stable complexes with the target proteins, particularly 2BL9 and 4ZL4. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) analysis showed that analog-3 complexes remained stable throughout the 500 ns simulation, while analog-2 exhibited greater fluctuations. Similarly, the root mean square fluctuation (RMSF) results indicated that analog-3 had lower residue fluctuations, suggesting stronger binding interactions and structural rigidity. The radius of gyration (Rg) analysis showed that analog-3 maintained a more compact structure, reinforcing its stability over time. In addition, solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) analysis revealed that analog-3 complexes had lower exposure to solvents, further confirming their structural integrity. These findings demonstrated that analog-3 is more stable than analog-2, which supports its potential as a more effective inhibitor. The combined docking and MD results suggest that analog-3 could be a promising candidate for enzyme inhibition applications.

The binding free energy (MM-PBSA) analysis provided further validation of the strong interactions between analog-3 and its target proteins. The results showed that analog-3 consistently exhibited lower binding energy values compared to analog-2, indicating stronger ligand-protein binding. The electrostatic interactions of analog-3–2BL9 were significantly stronger, contributing to its stability in the binding pocket. Additionally, van der Waals forces played an important role in stabilizing the ligand-protein complexes, particularly in analog-3–4ZL4 interactions. The MM-PBSA calculations confirmed that analog-3 formed more stable complexes, which correlated with the findings from docking and MD simulations. These results reinforce the hypothesis that analog-3 has a high potential for enzyme inhibition due to its strong and stable interactions with key residues. However, despite these promising findings, binding energy alone is not sufficient to determine drug-like properties (Fakih et al. 2021). Therefore, pharmacokinetic and toxicity evaluations were necessary to assess the feasibility of analog-3 as a drug candidate.

The absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) analysis indicated that all pipecolisporin analogs exhibited poor gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, which could limit their potential for oral administration. Additionally, none of the analogs were able to penetrate the blood-brain barrier (BBB), suggesting that they may not be effective for central nervous system (CNS) applications. Furthermore, all analogs were identified as P-gp substrates, which means they could be actively transported out of cells, potentially reducing their intracellular concentrations. On the other hand, the toxicity analysis showed that none of the analogs exhibited hepatotoxicity or cardiotoxicity, indicating a relatively safe profile in terms of liver and heart toxicity. However, neurotoxicity, respiratory toxicity, and immunotoxicity were detected in all analogs, which could pose challenges in drug development. These findings suggest that structural modifications will be necessary to enhance the pharmacokinetic properties and reduce potential toxicity risks (Shah et al. 2022). Although analog-3 demonstrated strong binding and stability, these pharmacokinetic limitations highlight the need for further optimization.

Despite the pharmacokinetic challenges, analog-3 exhibited promising enzyme inhibition activity, particularly as a potential protease inhibitor. The biological activity assessment showed that analog-3 had weak activity as a GPCR ligand, ion channel modulator, and kinase inhibitor, but it demonstrated slight protease inhibition potential. This suggests that analog-3 could still be valuable in targeting protease-related diseases, despite its pharmacokinetic drawbacks. The results indicate that structural optimization efforts should focus on improving bioavailability while maintaining strong binding affinity. Future studies should explore chemical modifications to enhance GI absorption and minimize toxicity, which could make analog-3 a viable drug candidate. Finally, analog-3 was identified as the most promising compound, exhibiting the best binding affinity, stability, and interaction strength among all tested pipecolisporin derivatives. However, to develop it into a potential drug, further structural refinements and experimental validation are necessary to overcome pharmacokinetic and toxicity challenges.

Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of pipecolisporin analogs as enzyme inhibitors, particularly in their interaction with protease targets. Among the six analogs, analog-3 exhibited the most promising activity, demonstrating strong binding affinities and stable interactions in molecular dynamics simulations, especially with the 2BL9 and 4ZL4 proteins. However, the pharmacokinetic analysis revealed poor gastrointestinal absorption and limited bioavailability due to P-gp substrate activity, indicating challenges for oral administration. While the

analogs showed no hepatotoxicity or cardiotoxicity, the presence of neurotoxicity and respiratory toxicity raises concerns that must be addressed. Despite these limitations, analog-3, with further optimization and toxicity reduction, possesses the necessary characteristics to be explored as a potential therapeutic agent. These findings suggest that pipecolisporin analogs, with structural improvements, could be promising candidates for the development of enzyme-targeting therapies.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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- The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.
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Author contributions

NK: performed computational experiments, collected and analyzed data, and drafted the manuscript; TMF: performed computational experiments, collected and analyzed data; RM: supervised, analyzed data, and revised the manuscript; US: supervised and revised the manuscript; ATH: supervised and revised the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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